

A Study on Consumer Behaviour towards Hamam Soap in Harur Taluka

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Abstract

The marketing scenario in India has undergone vast change since 1991 due to the economic reforms. Post-liberalization, competition intensified in every product line and market, which forced brands to redefine their norms of existence in all industries. In the FMCG industry, especially in the toilet soap sector, there has been severe competition among the MNCs, national and local players. Brand loyalty is determined by several distinct psychological processes of the consumers and entails multivariate measurements. Product features (Fragrance / Skin care / Germ fight features /Colour) is one of the most important factors that affect brand loyalty. The relationship between the availability of the toilet soap and the extent Of brand loyalty was also found to be significant. The toilet soaps can be divided into four price segments: Premium, popular, economy and carbolic soaps. At the same time, the penetration level of toilet soaps in urban areas is very high, but per Capita consumption levels remain low. In this scenario, it is very important for marketers to know the consumer behavior concerning toilet soaps, which will be very useful in adopting suitable strategies. This research paper attempts to Analyze the brand loyalty, satisfaction, awareness regarding Hamam soap in Harur Taluka, Dharmapuri District.

Keywords: Brand Awareness, Consumer Behaviour, Brand Loyalty, Harur, Hamam soap.

Introduction

Marketing is the process of communicating the value of a product or service to customers, to sell the product or service. It is a critical business function for attracting customers. From a societal point of view, marketing is the link between a society's material requirements and its economic patterns of response. Marketing satisfies these needs and wants through exchange processes and building long-term relationships. It is the process of communicating the value of a product or service through positioning to customers. Marketing can be looked at as an organizational function and a set of processes for creating, delivering and communicating value to customers, and managing customer relationships in ways that also

benefit the organization and its shareholders. Marketing is the science of Choosing target markets through market analysis and market segmentation, as well as understanding consumer buying behavior and providing superior customer value. There are five competing concepts under which organizations can choose to operate their business; the production concept, the product concept, the selling concept, the marketing concept, and the holistic marketing concept. The four components of holistic marketing are relationship marketing, internal marketing, integrated marketing, and socially responsive marketing. The set of engagements necessary for successful marketing management includes capturing marketing insights, connecting with customers, building strong brands, shaping the market offerings, delivering and communicating value, creating long-term growth, and developing marketing strategies and plans.

Meaning of Market

The word ‘Market’ is derived from the Latin word ‘Market’s’ meaning merchandise, wares, traffic, trade or a place where business is conducted. The common usage of the market means a place where goods are bought or sold.

Definition of Market

”Market refers to both place and region in which buyers and sellers are in free competition with one another.” –Pyle.

“The term market refers not to a place, but commodity or commodities and buyers and sellers who are in direct competition with one another.” – Chapman.

Meaning of Marketing

The management process through which goods and services move from concept to the customer. It includes the coordination of four elements called the 4 P’s of marketing: Identification, selection and development of a product,

Determination of its price, Selection of a distribution channel to reach the customer’s place, and Development and implementation of a promotional strategy. The essence of marketing is an exchange or a transaction, intended to satisfy human needs or wants. That is marketing is a human activity directed at satisfying needs and wants, through an exchange of process. A demand is a want for which the consumer is prepared to pay the price.

Definition of Marketing

According To Kotler “Marketing Is A Social And Managerial Process By Which Individuals And Groups Obtain What They Need And Want Through Creating, Offering And Exchanging Products Of Value With Others.”

Consumer Behavior

The Term Consumer Behaviour Is Defined As ‘The Behaviour That Consumers Display In Searching For Purchasing, Using, Evaluating And Disposing Of Products, Services And Ideas Which They Expect, Will Satisfy Their Needs.’ The Study Of Consumer Behaviour Is An Attempt To Understand And Predict Actions In The Buying Role. Engel Roger And D. Blackwell Say That “Buying Behaviour Is The Decision In Buying And Using Products.” Consumer Behaviour Is Defined As The Behaviour Exhibited By People In Planning, Purchasing And Using Economic Goods And Services. Consumer Behaviour Is An Integral Part Of Human Behaviour And Cannot Be Separated From It. Human Behaviour Refers To The Total Process By Which Individuals Interact With Their Environment. Consumer Is He King And It Is The Consumer Who Determines

What A Business Is. Therefore A Sound Marketing Programmer Should Start With A Careful Analysis Of The Habits, Attitudes, Motives And Needs Of Consumers. In Particular, A Marketer Should Find Answer To The Following Questions:

- What are the products they buy?
- Why they buy them?
- How they buy them?
- When they buy them?
- Where they buy them?
- How they buy them?
- Who is important in the buying decision?

The goal of the study of consumer behavior is to properly describe, explain and ultimately predict human actions in the market place. Understanding the consumer behaviour is not an easy job because of complexity involved the difficult in fully understanding of consumers needs which is often a costly and inexact process. The wealth of product and service produced in a country makes the economy strong. Almost all the products which are available to buyers have some alternative supplies, i.e., substitute products. Therefore a seller, most of his time, seek buyers and tries to please them. To be a successful seller, he must know:

- Who is a customer?
- What do consumers buy?
- When do they buy?
- How do they buy?
- Why do they buy?

A buyer purchases a particular brand and this can be termed as “product buying motives.” The reason behind the purchase from a particular seller is “patronage motives.”

Scope of the Study

The present study would help the dealer to know the Consumer Behaviour of the respondents towards Hamam soap and various soap brands. This would help the company to determine the promotional measures based on the findings. The company can adopt the promotional measures in and around Harur Taluka as this study was conducted there.

Objectives of the Study

Following are the objectives of the present study:

- To know the socio-economic profile of the consumers of the Hamam soap.
- To determine the most influencing factor in the purchase of the Hamam soap.
- To know the source of influence in the purchase of Hamam soap.
- To know the pattern of usages of the Hamam soap.
- To study the satisfaction of the consumers towards the Hamam soap based on the various products.
- To give suggestions based on the study for the improvement of the product.

Research Design

A research design work is a specified framework for controlling the data collection. It is the basic plan, which guides the data collection & analysis phases of the research project. This study is based on analysis of data so that the present work is an analytical study, which tries to analyze the view of the customers using the information collected from them.

To achieve the objectives of this study, the researcher collected the data from the customers and

then analysis was done. In social science there are two outstanding research methods:

- Primary data
- Secondary data

This study is based on both primary and secondary data.

Sampling Unit

Users of Hamam soap in Harur Taluka constitute the population of the present study.

Sampling size

In this survey, the sample size was determined as 150 arbitrarily.

Area of the study

This study has been undertaken in different parts of Harur taluka. Harur taluka, know as an important place, is the geographical area of this project work. Now this town is popular for school and collegiate educations. Some excellent matriculations school and arts and science colleges have been started for the last ten to fifteen years. At present, many arts & science colleges and teacher training institutions emerge to fulfill educational requirements of this area. The area has a heavy population, consisting of people from different walks of life.

Conclusion

Customers are the king of the market, superiors in an organization and Goose laying Eggs. Consumer Behaviour plays a significant role in modern marketing era. Soap is an important product for the day to day consumption of the customers. Nowadays competition is going on with a flame of advertisement war. A lot of varieties of soap are being introduced by several producers. In these competition situations, some soap because of evil effects due to a mixture of chemical compounds. People need quality of soap for which they are ready to have brand loyalty or switch over from one brand to another. To capture the needs of all the segments of people, the products are introduced in different quantity for perfect quality of users if it so, the soap will bring more market potential for soap.

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Suggestions

- Most of the respondents are under the age group of 20-30 years so the company should take Efforts to attract other age group people to increase their sales.
- Most of the respondents are under the income group of 5000 to 10000 per month. So the company should take efforts to position their products in this group in order increase their sales
- As quality is the first influencing factor of the company has to focus on quality and improve it for better sales.
- The company may give more offer and discount to improve the sales.

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